

Reconstruction of a Continuous Flow Field from Discrete Experimental Data Points using Physics-Informed Neural Networks

Mattias E. G. Eck^{1*}, Jakob G. R. von Saldern^{2†}, Philipp zur Nedden^{1†},
Alessandro Orchini^{3†}, Christian Oliver Paschereit^{1†}

^{1*}Chair of Fluid Dynamics, Technische Universität Berlin, Germany.

²Laboratory for Flow Instabilities and Dynamics,
Technische Universität Berlin, Germany.

³Chair of Nonlinear Thermo-Fluid Mechanics, Technische Universität Berlin,
Germany.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): m.eck@tu-berlin.de;

†These authors contributed equally to this work.

Abstract

Gas turbine combustors commonly feature swirling flows. The swirl is usually characterized by the swirler geometry. The development of swirl-stabilized burners includes the experimental assessment of the resulting flow field and the quantification of the swirl, e.g. through Laser Doppler Anemometry (LDA). LDA accurately acquires flow velocity components in a small probing volume. Nevertheless, the measurement quality represents a trade-off between invested measurement time and spatial resolution. In this work, the potential of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) to assimilate flow fields from sparse LDA measurements is investigated. A novel burner is employed in which the swirl is fluidically adjustable from a non-swirled jet to a fully swirled flow through a secondary air flow injection. Data is acquired through LDA within spatial measurement grids at multiple axial distances from the swirler. Assuming symmetry, axial, tangential, and radial velocity components are determined. A PINN is subsequently trained with the acquired data, creating a continuous and differentiable flow field representation by evaluating RANS equations. By systematically reducing the training data while evaluating the physical validity of the reconstructed field, a minimum training data requirement is identified. As a result, for three operating conditions, the flow field is adequately characterized by a minimum of measurement points.

Keywords: Swirling Flows, PINNs

1 Introduction

The efficiency of combustion processes within modern gas turbines strongly depends on fuel-air mixing, heat transfer mechanisms, and flame stability. To address these aspects and ensure a reliable flame anchoring, combustors incorporate a swirler element which imparts a defined swirl on the air flowing through the burner [1, 2]. The thermal-flow mechanisms within swirl-stabilized flames have been extensively studied [2–5]. In this respect, and particularly in the context of novel carbon-free fuels which require fuel flexibility, the ability to actively vary the degree of swirl offers a significant advantage [3], as it can aid the in-depth investigation of different flames stabilized by the same burner. In this context, we have developed a novel burner concept capable of an active and continuous swirl variation [6]. The burner solely relies on fluidic actuation, i.e. the controlled injection of a secondary air mass flow, and allows to vary the flow regime from a non-swirled axial jet to a fully swirled flow. The underlying working principle has been first qualitatively demonstrated through numerical simulations and then experimentally validated through Laser Doppler Anemometry (LDA) [7]. While LDA was found to be a suitable technique to characterize the flow velocity profiles, it only acquires velocity data for sparsely distributed measurement points, and accurate LDA measurements require long data acquisition periods at each measurement position. As a result, the quality of LDA measurements is governed by a trade-off between the measurement time and the spatial resolution of the collected data points.

To encounter such trade-offs, data assimilation techniques can be employed which allow for the identification of missing quantities, the expansion of limited domains, or the increase of resolution within sparse data points. In this regard, established tools include the extended Kalman filter [8, 9], or variational data assimilation [10, 11].

In recent years, the method of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) has emerged as a promising data processing tool [12]. The method allows to solve partial differential equations and to identify missing quantities based on available measurements through data assimilation [13]. The promising method rapidly became popular and is now frequently used in fluid mechanics [13–20]. Eivazi et al. demonstrate the capability of solving Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations using PINNs [16]. Molnar et al. employ PINNs for assimilating supersonic flow fields based on background-oriented schlieren measurements [15]. Von Saldern et al. utilize PINNs to assimilate the mean tangential velocity component from mono-PIV data of a swirling flow [21]. Patel et al. underline the mean flow data assimilation capabilities of PINNs by comparing it to the variational assimilation approach [17]. Steinfurth and Weiss apply PINNs to reconstruct a three-dimensional mean flow over a backward-facing step [19]. Villié et al. enhance velocity measurements obtained through magnetic resonance imaging using PINNs [20]. Hasanuzzaman et al. use PINNs to reconstruct the mean velocity field from two-dimensional three-component stereo-PIV datasets [22]. In [23], Eivazi et al. substantiate the ability of PINNs to catalyze high-resolution flow field data from incomplete and noisy reference data sets. Hanrahan et al. utilize PINNs to investigate turbulent flows and, for instance, show that wall shear stress and wall pressure can accurately be reconstructed from typical sparse training data [24]. In this regard, Hosseini and Shiri demonstrate the assimilation quality of PINNs and its efficiency, investigating a flow around a cylinder as a case study, with three distinct training sets [25]. In [26], Liu et al. apply PINNs to turbulent combustion, reconstructing velocity, temperature and species mass fractions from sparse data, comparing

the results to high-fidelity direct numerical simulation data. Furthermore, Arzani et al. corroborate the width of possible PINN applications by improving wall shear stress quantification in diseased arterial blood flows [27].

The present work demonstrates the potential of Physics-Informed Neural Networks to assimilate continuous flow fields from sparsely distributed LDA measurement points. With regard to the applications of PINNs found in literature, the present work focuses on the utilization of experimental LDA data, simultaneously yielding three velocity components along a grid of sparse measurement locations. For three different operation points, namely featuring no swirl, an intermediate degree of swirl, and a fully swirled flow regime, LDA experimental data was first acquired within discrete spatial measurement grids at various axial distances from the swirler’s outlet. This data was then used to train PINN models, which yield a continuous representation of the flow field, allowing for further in-depth analysis of the setup. The PINNs are trained using a composite loss function that considers both available data and compliance with physics. The LDA measurements serve as training data, while the physics are taken into account through the evaluation of the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations.

The consideration of the physics is especially advantageous since it allows for the accurate reconstruction of all three velocity components characterizing the respective flow field. This aspect in particular will be exploited in the present work. The acquisition of the radial velocity component \bar{u}_r has proven to be difficult due to its comparatively low values. Here we apply the PINN method to assimilate the radial velocity component based on the axial and tangential velocity components and the RANS equations. Additionally, for each operating point, the amount of training data used is systematically reduced while evaluating the physical validity of the computed flow field. As a result, the possibility to properly characterize a complex flow field through a minimum amount of required experimental training data is demonstrated.

2 Methodology

2.1 Experimental Test Facility

The experimental data for the flow field characterization was acquired through LDA measurements under atmospheric and non-reacting conditions. Details on the test facility are schematically depicted in Fig. 1, and summarized in the following. Details and results can be furthermore found in [7]. The open test facility primarily consists of an air plenum connected to the fluidic burner. The primary air is led into the plenum through a filtered air supply, controlled by Mass Flow Controllers (MFCs). The secondary air is directly induced through a separate MFC. Seeding particles are injected into the primary air flow through an apposite atomizer, needed for LDA measurements. The distributed particles have a median diameter of below 1 μm and it is assumed that the particle movement reliably resolves the flow. The average Reynolds number, based on the burner outlet diameter D , is kept constant at $Re \approx 10^5$, along with the total air mass flow $\dot{m}_{\text{tot}} = \dot{m}_p + \dot{m}_s$, amounting to a constant bulk velocity u_{Bulk} for all investigated conditions. The Mass Flow Ratio (MFR) between secondary and primary air is defined as $\text{MFR} = \frac{\dot{m}_s}{\dot{m}_p}$. Three MFR values corresponding to operating points with different degrees of swirl are investigated: (i) a non-swirled jet at $\text{MFR} = 6\%$; (ii) a flow subjected to an intermediate degree of swirl at $\text{MFR} = 10\%$; and (iii) a fully swirled flow at $\text{MFR} = 30\%$.

The employed 2D LDA system by *Dantec* relies on a two-color, four-beams laser system, featuring a 490 mW argon-ion laser by *Spectra-Physics*. Each of the colored beams is split in

Fig. 1 Left: Experimental setup used to study the fluidic burner. Right: Schematic of the LDA setup [7].

two, and one of each is led through a 40 MHz Bragg-Cell, where they are subjected to a frequency shift for directional sensitivity of the system. All four beams are then led through an integrated transmitting and receiving optic unit, which configures multiple beam parameters and simultaneously captures scattered and reflected light signals from seeding particles passing through the measurement volume. The focal length is set to $f = 310$ mm. For each emitted wavelength, the scattered light signals are processed through a photomultiplier, allowing for the simultaneous acquisition of two orthogonal velocity components in the Cartesian plane perpendicular to the laser-optic axis. The signal bursts are then analyzed in a Burst Spectrum Analyzer (BSA, Model *Dantec* BSA F60), which computes physical velocity values for each particle passing through the measurement volume within a given measurement time. For every measurement point, a velocity is inferred for each seeding particle (separately for each laser-velocity-component), registered in a statistically significant amount of particle data within a given measurement time. A pronounced axial symmetry of the flow field downstream of the novel burner has been observed and demonstrated [7]. In consequence, the experimental data used in this work could be advantageously acquired relying on measurements with a spatial location distribution following X-shaped grids, assuming an axisymmetric flow distribution. Here, the measurement locations are distributed along straight beams, aligned with the x and y coordinate axes for various constant axial distances z . In this regard, the used LDA setup can directly be used to acquire the respective tangential velocity components along one measurement point beam, the radial velocity components along the other, while acquiring the axial velocity for all measurement points. The use of X-shaped grids is found to be advantageous because it allows for a time-optimized assessment of the investigated flow field.

As a result, experimental data consisting of time-averaged cylindrical velocity components has been acquired (axial: \bar{u}_z , radial: \bar{u}_r , and tangential: \bar{u}_t). The utilized X-grids comprise measurement positions between radial locations of $0 \leq r/D \leq 2.94$, respectively distributed over up to ten axial distances from the burner outlet (i.e. $z/D = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 9, 10$).

2.2 Physics-Informed Neural Networks

PINNs allow to approximate given data with a neural network and take physics constraints in the form of partial differential equations into account during network training [12]. As a result, the trained neural network approximates both the given data and a solution to a given set of equations. In the present work, PINNs are applied to reconstruct time-averaged LDA velocity fields and to approximate a solution of the RANS equations [21]. The concept and the most important equations are briefly presented below, for further details we refer the interested reader to the literature [12, 16, 21].

A neural network is set up that maps spatial coordinates to the mean flow quantities:

$$[\bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha, \bar{p}_\alpha, \nu_\alpha] = \mathbf{f}_\alpha(z, r), \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha = [\bar{u}_{\alpha,z}, \bar{u}_{\alpha,r}, \bar{u}_{\alpha,t}]$ is the mean velocity vector, \bar{p}_α is the mean modified pressure, ν_α is the eddy viscosity and z and r are the axial and radial coordinates. The neural network is denoted by \mathbf{f}_α , where α represents the vector of trainable network parameters. The optimal values for these parameters, α^* , are found by minimizing a composite loss function that constrains the PINN outputs to the measured data, physics equations, and additional boundary conditions:

$$\alpha^* = \arg \min_{\alpha} \mathcal{L}(\alpha), \quad \mathcal{L}(\alpha) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{bc}}. \quad (2)$$

Here, λ_1 and λ_2 are weights that allow to shift the focus of network training between the individual constraints. The first term, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$, is the data loss term that penalizes deviations from the PINN output to available data points. In the present work, the measured axial and azimuthal velocities are used as training data:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} = \frac{1}{N_z N_r} \sum_i^{N_z} \sum_j^{N_r} (\bar{u}_{\alpha,z}(z_i, r_j) - \bar{u}_z^*(z_i, r_j))^2 + (\bar{u}_{\alpha,t}(z_i, r_j) - \bar{u}_t^*(z_i, r_j))^2, \quad (3)$$

where the *-superscript denotes a measured quantity. N_z and N_r denote the total number of axial and radial measured locations which correspond to the number of measured planes and the number of measurement positions within each plane respectively. Due to the relatively low signal to noise ratio, the radial velocity component is omitted. Similarly to the weights in equation (2), additional weights could be introduced to take into account measurement uncertainty. These additional losses could even be used locally, provided that a measure for the respective noise is known for each measurement point. In the present case, we only exclude the radial velocity component as the quality of the results significantly differs when compared to the axial and azimuthal velocity components over the entire measurement grid.

To evaluate the physics loss, the PINN output quantities are substituted into the incompressible RANS equations with the Boussinesq eddy viscosity model:

$$(\bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha \cdot \nabla) \bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha + \nabla \bar{p}_\alpha - \nabla \cdot [(\nu + \nu_\alpha) [\nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha + \nabla \bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha^T]] = \mathbf{e}_1, \quad (4a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha = \mathbf{e}_2, \quad (4b)$$

where \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 denote the residual of the RANS equations and the continuity equation, respectively. The density is assumed to be constant and is included into the pressure. The residuals are evaluated at N_c discrete points sampled across the domain. The averaged residuals form the physics loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_i^{N_c} \left(\|r_i \mathbf{e}_1(z_i, r_i)\|_2^2 + |r_i \mathbf{e}_2(z_i, r_i)|^2 \right), \quad (5)$$

where the residuals are locally weighted with the radial coordinate to avoid division by zero on the central axis. Similar to the data and the physics loss term, boundary conditions are implemented by adding a third loss term, \mathcal{L}_{bc} . The term enforces zero radial and tangential velocities on the symmetry axis, zero axial and tangential velocities for large radii, zero radial derivative of the axial velocity component on the symmetry axis, and no-slip boundary conditions on the upstream located wall (burner base plate, also see Fig. 2). All constraints in Eq. (2) are taken into account in the form of deviations at discrete points (also referred to as collocation points) in the cost function. However, the PINN is a continuous function which, once trained, can be evaluated at any point in space. In this work, network architectures with five layers of 20 neurons each are used. The activation functions are chosen to be hyperbolic tangents for all layers except for the output layer, where linear functions are used.

As shown in equation (2), the weights λ_1 and λ_2 allow for a shift of the network training focus between the individual constraints, i.e. between physics, boundary conditions, and data. The used RANS and continuity equations involve five unknowns: the three components of velocity, pressure, and the eddy viscosity field. Thus, to solve this system of equations as a boundary value problem without any training data, an additional turbulence closure equation for the eddy viscosity would be required. In the present work, we make use of the available training data to provide additional information to the model during training, instead of including such a closure model. Accordingly, the objective is to acquire the missing fields from the provided velocity fields. In this respect, the weights are selected to prioritize the data loss term, as also shown in § 3.1.

Figure 2 schematically depicts the resulting analysis domain used in the present study. Here, the collocation points are depicted as blue dots, and are randomly distributed within the area of interest. Despite the ability of the PINN-approach to reconstruct physical quantities within a deliberately chosen domain, in the current study, the model is evaluated within the limits of the used experimental domain. Thus, the collocation points are distributed accordingly, and an extrapolation of physical quantities outside the range of experimental domain is not considered. For extrapolation beyond the measurement domain, a closed set of equations, including a turbulence model, would have to be taken into account.

3 Results

In this section, key features of the reconstructed flow fields are presented and discussed. At first, the physical validity of the PINN approach is discussed and validated. In this regard, its ability to reconstruct velocity data as provided during the respective training is evaluated. Moreover, the quality of the respective predictions in between training data locations is assessed through the respective physics loss. Subsequently, the reconstructed axial flow

Fig. 2 Analysis domain. With the assumption of axial symmetry, the domain is depicted as a half longitudinal section. Flow direction from left to right.

Fig. 3 Weighted losses \mathcal{L} over training iterations, exemplary shown for MFR = 30%. Total loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}}$ shown in blue, data loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ shown in orange and physics loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$ shown in green.

velocity \bar{u}_z and its distribution is discussed and compared between the three examined cases. Analogously, the reconstructed radial and tangential velocity components \bar{u}_r and \bar{u}_t are discussed. Eventually, the optimization of the approach in terms of used training data is illustrated. As axial symmetry is assumed, the presented results are shown within the domain as a half longitudinal section.

3.1 PINN Training Process

The components within the PINN's composite loss function can be weighted to respectively leverage particular constraints during the training process (see §2.2). In the current study, the weights are selected to prioritize the data loss term. Fig. 3 exemplary shows the weighted losses over the completed function calls for one operating condition. In this regard, the composite loss is stored at each function call, with approximately three function calls representing one training iteration. The minimization of the composite loss function shows to be well converged. After approximately 80,000 function calls, the total loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}}$, as well as all of its components, are not further minimized. As can be observed, the data loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ dominates the overall loss.

Fig. 4 Reconstructed and measured \bar{u}_z , \bar{u}_t , and \bar{u}_r over r/D for MFR = 10% at $z/D = 6$.

This was achieved by accordingly adjusting the training weights λ_1 and λ_2 in the composite loss function (see equation (2)). With a comparatively high weight on the data loss, this term is prioritized during training, enabling the network to closely match the available data. This is essential, as the absence of a turbulence closure model requires the network to infer missing information from the data. However, a strong weighting on the data loss does not mean that flow physics are neglected. As shown in Fig. 3, the physics loss $\mathcal{L}_{\text{physics}}$ is also minimized during training.

3.2 Comparison of Reconstructed Quantities to Experimental Data

As described in §2.2, the used PINN is trained with time averaged velocity data, experimentally acquired through LDA, and creates a differentiable and continuous representation of the underlying flow field, which can be evaluated at any given spatial location. The data is not merely interpolated, but takes physics into consideration by relying on RANS equations. However, the applicability of this approach strongly depends on its ability to adequately reconstruct the quantities used as training data. Alongside the working principle of the employed PINN, this can be evaluated through the discussion of the differences between measured and reconstructed quantities at the respective measurement locations. For this purpose, for an exemplary operating condition, all three reconstructed velocity components are compared to the respective training data at an exemplary axial review position. In the following, results for the intermediate-swirl case are presented (MFR = 10% with a swirl number of $S \approx 0.4$ [7]), as it is found to adequately represent flow field characteristics of the entire operating range. In this regard, Fig. 4 depicts the comparison of reconstructed and measured \bar{u}_z (left), \bar{u}_t (middle), and \bar{u}_r (right) over r/D for MFR = 10% at $z/D = 6$.

What becomes evident, is the ability of the PINN model to create a smooth representations of the underlying flow field, despite the noise to which the experimental training data is subjected. As shown in the left plot of Fig. 4, the PINN prediction complies well to the training data for \bar{u}_z , both qualitatively and quantitatively. A similar finding can be observed for the azimuthal velocity component \bar{u}_t shown in the middle Fig. 4. The PINN model processes

the experimental training data and combines it with underlying physics, represented by the RANS equations. Through the imposed physics, alongside the chosen boundary conditions, physical information is included into the assimilation process. As a result values for which the experimental evaluation does not yield results of sufficient physical quality are corrected.

Compared to the axial and azimuthal velocity components, the radial velocity exhibits significantly lower magnitudes. Given the accuracy limitations of the measurement equipment, this results in a low signal-to-noise ratio, as illustrated in the right plot of Fig. 4. The data appear highly fluctuating and do not exhibit a clear velocity profile. Consequently, the radial velocity component was excluded from the training dataset for the PINN model. Nonetheless, the PINN is able to assimilate \bar{u}_r throughout the domain solely based on the axial and azimuthal velocity components used as training data, as well as the evaluation of the physics loss. The \bar{u}_r profile shown in Fig. 4 exhibits the expected behavior at $x/D = 6$. On the centerline, the radial velocity is zero; as the radius increases, it rises due to the expansion of the jet. In the outer region of the shear layer, the radial velocity decreases and becomes negative, indicating the entrainment of ambient air.

The investigated PINN-based approach is therefore found to yield results of high agreement with the training data, supplemented by the consideration of the flow physics. To validate the results also in regions where no training data was used, the physics loss is inspected in detail in the next section.

3.3 Physical Reconstruction Quality

As stated in § 3.2, the quality of the PINN models used in the present study can be determined through the evaluation of the residual of the physics loss, as introduced in Eqs. (4a) and (4b). The validity of the PINN predictions between training locations strictly depend on it. For the evaluation of the physical predictions, the component of the physics loss concerning the conservation of mass [see Eq. (4b)] is exemplary discussed and evaluated for an exemplary operating condition (MFR = 10%). It quantifies the local violation of the mass conservation within each cell of the domain. From Eq. (4b) follows:

$$\mathbf{e}_2 = \nabla \cdot \bar{\mathbf{u}}_\alpha = \frac{d\bar{u}_{\alpha,z}}{dz} + \frac{d\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}}{dr} + \frac{\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}}{r}. \quad (6)$$

Figure 5 exemplary depicts the normalized residual of the mass conservation equation and all of its components, each spatially evaluated over the analysis domain. In this regard, all input parameters and, thus, the quantities in equation (6) are initially normalized through the mixing tube diameter D and the bulk flow velocity u_{Bulk} , respectively. Here, \mathbf{e}_2 is shown over the analysis domain (bottom plot), as well as all its components: $|d\bar{u}_{\alpha,z}/dz|$, $|d\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}/dr|$, and $|\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}/r|$. It can be observed that the residual of the continuity equations reaches its maximum in the region $z/D < 1$. This pronounced violation of mass conservation is expected, since the PINN is exclusively trained in the region between $z/D = 1$ and $z/D = 10$. Within the training region, it can be observed that the residual of the continuity equation (last row) is substantially lower compared to its individual components (row 1-3). In most regions, the residual of the sum is two to four orders of magnitude lower compared to its components. It can therefore be concluded that the PINN has assimilated a velocity field that complies with the continuity

Fig. 5 Mass conservation residual e_2 (bottom) and its components: $|d\bar{u}_{\alpha,z}/dz|$ (first), $|d\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}/dr|$ (second), and $|\bar{u}_{\alpha,r}/r|$ (third), for MFR = 10% (at ref. case).

equation. This agreement with the underlying physics validates the PINN approach for regions between training data points within the analysis domain.

3.4 Reconstructed Axial Velocity Fields (\bar{u}_z)

The employed PINN model, trained with the data from all available measurement data, i.e. with data from all 10 measurement planes, is set to be the reference case. It therefore comprises the maximum amount of experimental information and, thus, its predicted results comprise the highest validity. As a result, it is well suited for the discussion of the reconstructed flow fields. In this respect, Fig. 6 depicts the reconstructed flow velocity distribution for all analyzed operating conditions (MFR = 6%, 10%, 30%).

Fig. 6 Reconstructed axial velocity component \bar{u}_z for MFR = 6% (top), 10% (middle), and 30% (bottom) at reference case. The streamlines within the shown half longitudinal section of the reconstructed flow in the $r-z$ plane are shown in black.

At MFR = 6%, an operating condition is experimentally identified featuring no swirl (swirl number $S \approx 0$, see [7]). The resulting axial jet is accordingly reconstructed by the PINN approach. Close to the burner outlet, characteristically, values of \bar{u}_z are predicted amounting

to approx. 100% of u_{Bulk} . With increasing axial distance z/D , through the entrainment of surrounding air, the axial jet widens, resulting in a even velocity distribution over a wider radial range.

The case depicted in the middle of Fig. 6 denotes an operating condition at an intermediate degree of swirl ($S \approx 0.4$) at MFR = 10%. The distribution of axial velocity follows a similar trend as for the aforementioned non-swirled case. However, despite the absence of areas with a reversed axial flow, indicating the absence of a vortex break-down, \bar{u}_z is reduced to approx. 20% of u_{Bulk} towards the center-line close to the burner outlet. This demonstrates the swirled nature of the flow field, thus clearly distinguishing the operating condition from the one at MFR = 6%. Additionally, with increasing z/D , the swirling jet spreads at a higher rate, resulting in a jet diameter of approx. $2 \cdot D$ at $z/D = 10$. Consequently, at the end of the analysis domain, \bar{u}_z peaks at approx. 35% of u_{Bulk} at the center-line. The depicted streamlines, accordingly, indicate a higher degree of entrainment, especially at $z/D \geq 5$.

For MFR = 30%, the \bar{u}_z component shows an area close to the mixing tube outlet, at $r/D \leq 0.5$ and $z/D \leq 2$, with a pronounced reversed flow, peaking at approximately 40% of the bulk velocity. This indicates the occurrence of a vortex breakdown creating a central recirculation zone, as is the case for swirling flows stabilized by state-of-the-art swirl burners. Accordingly, at this operating condition, the swirl number is experimentally identified as $S \approx 0.9$ (at $r/D = 1$, see [7]). The spatial extent of the observed recirculation zone appears to be limited, due to the limits of the investigation domain. Regions located in close axial vicinity to the burner reference plane (at $z/D < 1$) are herein not included and, thus, the area subjected to a reversed axial flow can be assumed to be further extended. For greater radii ($r/D > 0.5$), the local maximum of the axial velocity is reached (at approx. 58% of u_{Bulk}), resulting in pronounced axial velocity gradients close to the mixing tube outlet. With increasing z/D , the area of positive axial velocity increases, indicating the characteristics of a widening swirling jet, progressively entraining a growing amount of air with increasing axial distance. As a result, the overall values of \bar{u}_z decrease, imparting a uniform axial velocity distribution for $z/D \geq 8$.

3.5 Reconstructed Radial Velocity Fields (\bar{u}_r)

Analogously to the discussion in § 3.4, the radial velocity fields are discussed, as reconstructed through the PINN from the maximum amount of available training data. In this respect, Fig. 7 depicts the reconstructed radial velocity fields for all MFR cases. As mentioned in § 1, the experimental acquisition of the radial velocity component \bar{u}_r is found to be challenging with the chosen experimental approach, since the respective velocity magnitude strongly diverts from the other velocity components acquired simultaneously. As a result, \bar{u}_r is not used to train the PINNs, but solely assimilated by the inclusion of the physics loss. Hence, it can be used as a parameter to assess the quality of the reconstructed flow fields.

For MFR = 6%, as visible from the reconstructed \bar{u}_r depicted at the top of Fig. 7, for axial distances $z/D \geq 2$, the trend complies well to the progression of \bar{u}_z . Air is entrained along the entire outer domain border, visible from a region of negative \bar{u}_r for higher radii. At the same time, the axial jet expands, imprinting a positive \bar{u}_r within the inner domain region close to the jet's center-line. For $z/D \geq 2$, a characteristic continuous progression of \bar{u}_r can be observed, increasing with axial distance. Over the entire z/D range, nonetheless, for the non-swirled case, the overall magnitude of \bar{u}_r is found to be comparably low.

For the case featuring an intermediate swirl magnitude (see middle plot in Fig. 7), the intensity of \bar{u}_r is more pronounced, especially for $2 \leq z/D \leq 4$, peaking at approx. 4.5% of u_{Bulk} . The air rotation is sufficient for an increased spreading of the swirled jet, imprinting a higher radial air translation. At the same time, especially for higher axial distances, the air entrainment leads to elevated negative values for \bar{u}_r (approx. 2% of u_{Bulk}). In contrast to the non-swirled case, however, close to the center-line, an area featuring a low radial gradient of \bar{u}_r can be observed, combined with locally low absolute radial velocity magnitudes. This prediction confirms the presence of an imparted flow swirl.

At MFR = 30%, i.e. featuring a high degree of swirl, the central recirculation zone in vicinity of the burner outlet and its center-line significantly affects the radial velocity distribution. In contrast to the case at MFR = 10%, at low axial distances, high negative magnitudes of \bar{u}_r can be observed (at approx. 6.5% for $z/D = 2$). For $z/D \geq 3$, the progression of \bar{u}_r is qualitatively comparable to the one observed for MFR = 10%. Since the highly swirled jet is subjected to a higher expansion rate, the overall magnitudes of \bar{u}_r are however higher. Again, as observed for the intermediate-swirl case, an even more pronounced area of low radial velocity and of respective radial gradients is observed, at higher axial distance. Additionally,

Fig. 7 Reconstructed radial velocity component \bar{u}_r for MFR = 6% (top), 10% (middle), and 30% (bottom) at reference case. The streamlines of the reconstructed flow in the $r - z$ plane are shown in black.

for $z/D \geq 8$, the expansion of the swirled jet exceeds the spatial boundaries of the analysis domain, hence comprising values of $\bar{u}_r > 0$ over the entire radial extent.

3.6 Reconstructed Tangential Velocity Fields (\bar{u}_t)

Analogously and supplementary to the discussion in § 3.4 and 3.5, the tangential velocity fields are discussed, as reconstructed through the PINNs from the maximum amount of available training data. As shown in Fig. 8, the respectively reconstructed tangential velocity fields are herein depicted. In contrast to Figs. 6 and 7, Fig. 8 depicts the PINN representation of \bar{u}_t

Fig. 8 Reconstructed tangential velocity component \bar{u}_t for MFR = 10% (top) and 30% (bottom) at reference case. The streamlines of the reconstructed flow in the $r - z$ plane are shown in black.

only for the cases featuring a measurable degree of swirl, i.e MFR = 10% and 30%. Since the experimental training data for the non-swirled case comprise negligibly low magnitudes of \bar{u}_t , the tangential velocity throughout the domain can be assumed to be 0, especially considering the experimental uncertainty and the resulting quality of the training data.

For the operating condition at MFR = 10%, the magnitude of swirl imparts an observable tangential velocity distribution throughout the domain. Close to the burner's outlet (at $z/D \approx 2$), \bar{u}_t reaches its maximum values, peaking at approx. 50% of u_{Bulk} . Generally, for low z/D , the radial distribution is comparably narrow, with the aforementioned peak being located at $r/D \approx 0.25$. Towards $r/D = 1$, \bar{u}_t is abruptly decreased, even reaching slightly negative values (at approx. 1% of u_{Bulk} , denoting a negligibly low, locally constrained counter-rotating swirl). With increasing axial distance, the respective tangential velocity peak is mitigated, with the distribution extending over an increasing radial range. For $z/D \geq 5$, this results in a central region (at low radii), exhibiting \bar{u}_t magnitudes close to 0, with accordingly low radial gradients. Towards the end of the domain ($z/D \rightarrow 10$), the radial expansion of the swirling

Fig. 9 Validation loss for all MFR cases as a function of number of measurement planes used for training.

jet induces an air rotation over a radial range up to $r/D \approx 2.2$, featuring a radially uniform \bar{u}_t distribution at approx. 3% of u_{Bulk} .

At a high degree of swirl (MFR = 30%, see bottom of Fig. 8), close to the recirculation zone, a high tangential flow velocity is reconstructed, in the same order of magnitude as the respective \bar{u}_z . In contrast to MFR = 10%, this region comprises a slightly lower peak value, and extends over a wider radial range. For higher radial and axial distances, an increasing amount of air is entrained, enlarging the area of swirling fluid and simultaneously reducing \bar{u}_t . Towards the end of the domain for $z/D \rightarrow 10$, the swirling jet is completely expanded, resulting in an almost uniform \bar{u}_t distribution over the entire radial range. Compared to the intermediate-swirl case, at $z/D \rightarrow 10$, \bar{u}_t is found to stabilize at higher magnitudes, i.e. at approx. 4% of u_{Bulk} . The physically-sound features confirm that the trained PINN model correctly reconstructs the radial velocity field from the axial and tangential velocity data measured in the experiments.

3.7 PINN Training Optimization

One objective of this study is to explore how PINNs can be applied to reduce the amount of experimental data, and thus the experimental time and resources, needed to characterize the flow. To this end, a study is conducted in which the number of velocity planes used for training is gradually reduced. The performance of the assimilation is evaluated using a validation loss, \mathcal{L}_{val} , which quantifies the averaged squared difference between the PINN-predicted and measured mean axial and azimuthal velocity components across all 10 measurement locations. Thus, for the reference case – that is trained with all 10 planes – the validation loss corresponds to the data loss of the trained network, $\mathcal{L}_{val} = \mathcal{L}_{data}$. As the number of planes provided for training decreases, the validation loss increasingly reflects data that was not included during the training process.

The quality of the PINN approximations are evaluated for all operating conditions. Figure 9 depicts \mathcal{L}_{val} as a function of the number of supplied training data planes $N_{\text{Tr,planes}}$. As stated in § 3.3, the presented approach relies on normalized input data, not comprising any physical dimension. The calculated losses are correspondingly dimensionless. It can be seen that the loss magnitude depends on the operating condition. The largest error is observed for MFR = 30%, which has a high degree of swirl and, thus, creates a complex flow field with areas of reversed flow, as discussed in § 3.4. This is accompanied by increased unsteadiness and stronger fluctuations (noise), yielding a more complex flow field compared to non-swirled cases, which explains the increased loss. As expected, for all operating conditions, a clear trend is visible: the validation loss decreases with increasing number of provided training data planes. This trend persists up to $N_{\text{Tr,planes}} = 6$, after which the loss remains almost constant at a low level. Consequently, 6 planes are sufficient to approximate the flow in the range between $z/D = 1$ and $z/D = 10$. This result demonstrates that PINN-based data assimilation can be applied to reduce experimental effort.

The increase in assimilation error is likely caused by insufficient training data. As mentioned above, training data are required to compensate for the absence of a turbulence closure model for the eddy viscosity. When too little data are available, the assimilation process can fail. One possible solution is to incorporate a turbulence model for the eddy viscosity into the training process (e.g. see [17]). However, when providing a closed set of equations, caution is required, as turbulence models can be overly restrictive and may not align well with the available measured data.

4 Conclusions

A PINNs-based method for the reconstruction of continuous flow fields from sparse experimental data was presented. The method was tested on the flow fields generated by a novel burner concept, which allows for the active variation the flow’s swirl number. For three operating conditions, with no, intermediate, and full swirl, respectively, experimental data consisting of three cylindrical velocity components was acquired and used to train PINN models. The suitability of the approach was validated, and reference cases were defined for the three operating conditions. The reconstructed flow fields were discussed in detail, and the divergence of the reconstructed velocity components to the training data was used to quantify the accuracy of PINNs trained with sparse data, as well as the respective physics loss.

The work shows that the PINN method can be used to reconstruct flow fields with different characteristics, ranging from pure axial jets to fully swirled flows. Furthermore, it was shown for the considered domain of interest that a minimum amount of training data, at approximately six axial locations, is needed to yield accurate results, regardless of the operating point. PINNs hence have the potential to significantly reduce measurement expenses of complex measurement techniques and allow for the reconstruction of complex 3D flow fields from sparse LDA measurement data.

As a result, the exploitation of PINNs is well suited to be extended by applying the method to tasks featuring a higher degree of complexity. Among others, this can include assimilation of flow data outside the experimental domain (e.g. into the nozzle and the upstream and downstream domain). In this regard, additional measurements, experimental acquisition of key quantities, or the application of additional equations are required, e.g. in the form of closure models.

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Declarations

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